

Rethinking Denosumab Discontinuation: State of the Art and Proposal of an Innovative Algorithm for Fracture Risk Management Post-Denosumab

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Abstract

Background. Denosumab discontinuation is associated with a sharp rebound in bone turnover and increased incidence of (multiple vertebral) fractures within months. Current strategies often rely on a fixed serum C-terminal telopeptide (CTX) threshold to guide antiresorptive re-initiation, but are based on weak evidence and ignores patient-specific biological variability.

Objective. To critically examine the limitations of CTX-guided post-denosumab management and propose a dynamic, individualized approach based on reference change value (RCV), longitudinal CTX trends, and complementary clinical tools.

Methods. This narrative review integrates data from observational studies, pathophysiological principles, and clinical practice guidelines. Relevant literature was identified using PubMed, Scopus and Google Scholar, focusing on fracture risk after denosumab discontinuation, CTX, bone turnover markers (BTMs), bone mineral density (BMD), trabecular bone score (TBS), and emerging therapeutic alternatives for osteoporosis. The delta-RCV model was developed by applying the statistical concept of biological variability to individualized CTX monitoring.

Results. Evidence suggests as a fixed CTX threshold can lead to a substantial risk of overtreatment or missed intervention. Our proposed delta-RCV framework interprets significant CTX changes based on intra-individual variability, and it integrates with complementary tools for bone status evaluation.

Conclusion. Our dynamic, patient-specific approach based on CTX trajectories, RCV thresholds, and multimodal risk stratification may improve treatment timing, and reduce fracture risk post-denosumab. Due to these complexities, a careful and planned denosumab prescription and discontinuation, should be mandatory.

Introduction

Denosumab, a fully human monoclonal antibody that inhibits receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand (RANKL), has become a cornerstone in the treatment of osteoporosis due to its potent and sustained antiresorptive activity. Clinical trials have demonstrated its significant efficacy in increasing bone mineral density (BMD) and reducing the risk of vertebral, non-vertebral, and hip fractures, particularly in patients at high fracture risk [1].

However, the discontinuation of denosumab is associated with a well-documented rebound phenomenon: a rapid and profound increase in bone turnover markers, accelerated loss of BMD, and an elevated risk of multiple vertebral fractures, often occurring within months [2-4].

This rebound effect presents a critical clinical challenge in post-treatment management, for which no universally accepted strategy currently exists [5]. In clinical practice, a common approach to mitigate this risk involves monitoring serum levels of C-terminal telopeptide of type I collagen (CTX), a marker of bone resorption. A CTX threshold of 0.28 ng/mL is often used as a trigger for initiating a follow-up antiresorptive therapy, typically with intravenous zoledronic acid [6-9].

Despite its widespread use, this threshold is based on weak empirical evidence and does not account for the high biological and analytical variability of CTX, nor for the heterogeneity among osteoporotic patients [10][11]. CTX levels are influenced by multiple physiological and pathological factors, including circadian rhythm, sex, age, menopausal status, renal function, and comorbid conditions. Moreover, pre-analytical errors, inter-laboratory variability, and assay differences further limit the reliability of a fixed CTX cut-off [11][12].

To address these limitations, the concept of Reference Change Value (RCV) has been proposed, which quantifies the magnitude of change required to reflect a true biological variation beyond expected variability [10][13]. According to this model, a change of approximately 25–30% is needed to confidently interpret a rise in CTX as clinically meaningful. Nevertheless, current post-denosumab strategies remain rooted in static, one-size-fits-all thresholds that risk both overtreatment—exposing patients to unnecessary adverse effects—and undertreatment—failing to prevent fractures [4][14][15]. In this context, a shift toward a more individualized and dynamic monitoring paradigm is both necessary and timely [16][17].

Objectives

This narrative review aims to critically reassess the current clinical strategies employed after denosumab discontinuation, with particular focus on the limitations of using a fixed CTX threshold—most commonly 0.28 ng/mL—as a guide for therapeutic intervention.

Our review explores the physiological, analytical, and clinical weaknesses inherent to this static approach, emphasizing the substantial inter- and intra-individual variability in CTX levels and the influence of multiple biological and pre-analytical factors [11][12].

A central objective is to introduce and develop a dynamic, individualized model for monitoring bone turnover, grounded in the concept of RCV, which allows for the identification of meaningful biological variation in CTX over time [10]. This delta-based strategy is proposed as a more reliable alternative to fixed thresholds, enabling clinicians to tailor therapeutic decisions based on patient-specific trends rather than absolute values.

In addition, the review examines the broader framework of post-denosumab fracture risk stratification, integrating additional diagnostic classical tools and innovative ones (even if there is a profound lack of evidence in this setting) [18][19]. The analysis also includes a critical discussion of current and emerging therapeutic options, and considers how artificial intelligence (AI) and predictive modeling could support clinical decision-making in this complex transitional phase [10][20][21].

To resume, our review aims to promote a shift toward a more flexible, personalized, and data-informed approach, for the management of osteoporotic patients following denosumab discontinuation.

Materials and methods

This narrative review was conducted through a targeted literature search using PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus. Keywords included "denosumab discontinuation", "rebound phenomenon", "CTX", "reference change value (RCV)", "zoledronic acid", "romosozumab", "TBS", "bone turnover markers" and "osteoporotic fracture risk predictors". Articles were selected based on clinical relevance, scientific rigor, and pertinence/applicability to post-denosumab therapeutic decision-making. No article type and date restrictions were applied. Particular attention was given to papers describing the variability of CTX levels, the concept of RCV and its use in clinical settings, and outcomes following various sequential therapies post-denosumab. Methodological triangulation was applied by cross-referencing data from clinical trials with findings from real-world evidence and expert position statements to ensure a comprehensive and clinically grounded synthesis. In developing the delta-RCV conceptual model, biological variation data (specifically analytical and intra-individual variability of CTX) was extracted from existing literature, and a conservative estimate of significant change (25–30%) was adopted in line with published RCV thresholds [10]. Clinical plausibility and utility were further validated through interdisciplinary discussion among endocrinologists, internists, and researchers with experience in osteoporosis management.

Results and discussion

The literature consistently demonstrates that the rebound phenomenon following denosumab discontinuation is clinically significant, with sharp elevations in CTX levels, rapid loss of BMD, and an increased risk of vertebral fractures—particularly multiple vertebral fractures [2][4][5][22]. Fixed thresholds such as the 0.28 ng/mL CTX level, although used in clinical practice, have shown limited reliability due to the high inter-individual and analytical variability. This underscores the inadequacy of a one-size-fits-all approach [7][11].

The delta-RCV model proposed here introduces a patient-specific monitoring tool based on percentage changes from individual CTX baselines. Changes exceeding the RCV (25–30%) are considered clinically relevant. Such a model acknowledges the biological variability intrinsic to CTX and offers a more tailored interpretation of post-denosumab bone turnover.

TBS and BMD remain essential tools for assessing microarchitectural integrity and absolute bone mass, respectively. TBS has shown particular utility in detecting trabecular deterioration not reflected in BMD alone [18][19][23]. Moreover, the integration of BTMs—beyond CTX—such as alkaline phosphatase (ALP), bone alkaline phosphatase (B-ALP), lysylpyridinoline (LP), deoxypyridinoline (DPD), procollagen type 1 N-terminal propeptide (P1NP) or tartrate-resistant acid phosphatase 5b (TRAP5b)—may enhance diagnostic granularity, although further validation is needed [11][24].

Regarding treatment, zoledronic acid is commonly used after denosumab, but emerging data suggest that its efficacy may be suboptimal in some individuals, especially if the timing of administration is not well synchronized with CTX levels [6][7][9][25]. Romosozumab, an anabolic agent, has shown promise in increasing BMD and improving bone quality, making it a compelling candidate in high-risk cases where antiresorptive rebound must be mitigated quickly [11][20][26]. The inclusion of AI-based predictive tools in fracture risk assessment offer a potential leap forward in clinical decision-making. Early models integrating DXA data, clinical risk scores, and BTMs have demonstrated superior predictive accuracy compared to traditional tools alone [21][27][28].

Based on the aforementioned limitations and clinical insights, we propose a conceptual framework—the delta-RCV model—to guide post-denosumab management. This approach aims to replace the use of a universal CTX threshold with dynamic, intra-individual monitoring, where treatment decisions should be based on whether CTX increases exceed the patient-specific RCV. The model is based on the following principles: if denosumab must be discontinued (which should be planned in advance), a potent amino-bisphosphonate (e.g., zoledronic acid) should be administered 5–6 months after the last injection. Then, we suggest the following steps (see Figures 1, 2, and 3) to dynamically and multidimensionally assess patients' fragility fracture risk, and thereby determine when to initiate treatment or continue monitoring. (1) Avoid risky movements, apply fall prevention strategies and

adopt healthy lifestyle habits at the highest level achievable (e.g., healthy diet, age-appropriate physical activity, with specialist if needed, reduce/avoid smoke and alcohol). (2) Optimize serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels to 30–50 ng/mL and assess calcium intake to ensure adequate intake (at every visit/blood test). (3) Obtain serial CTX measurements (frequency established by physicians) and compare them to baseline values. (4) Calculate RCV-based thresholds to detect true biological changes, taking into account that the percentage change required may vary depending on the assay and laboratory-specific critical difference. (5) Interpret CTX trends in conjunction with other BTMs, such as ALP, B-ALP, and—where available consider—LP, DPD, P1NP and TRAP-5b (frequency established by physicians). (6) Estimate fracture risk based also on patient history and clinical characteristics, also using validated tool such as Fracture Risk Assessment Tool (FRAX[®])—at every visit—incorporating BTMs trend, dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) BMD—every 18-24 months—vertebral fracture assessment (VFA)—yearly or when clinically needed—and TBS (during DXA scan). Additional tools, such as quantitative ultrasound (QUS) or radiofrequency echographic multi-spectrometry (REMS), may be considered when available [29].

At each stage, additional tests should be considered, such as blood and urine examinations [e.g., serum calcium, 24-hour urine calcium, parathyroid hormone (PTH), serum creatinine, phosphorus, and magnesium levels], as well as imaging studies (e.g., radiography, magnetic resonance imaging).

Serial CTX monitoring is advised to inform clinical decisions based on temporal trends rather than isolated or paired values, which helps mitigate the limitations posed by CTX's biological and analytical variability. Furthermore, referring to a patient's baseline CTX level—measured at the first reassessment, 5–6 months after denosumab discontinuation—and evaluating whether it lies within the normal sex- and age-specific reference range (ideally aligned with the median of the lab's population-specific reference interval), provides a more personalized approach. This is particularly important in the absence of validated CTX thresholds stratified by age, sex, or ethnicity.

While empirical and currently unvalidated, our model aims to offer a rational and biologically coherent framework to guide future clinical applications and prospective studies.

Conclusion

The management of osteoporosis following denosumab discontinuation remains a complex clinical challenge, primarily due to the unpredictable rebound in bone turnover and fracture risk. Reliance on a static CTX threshold does not sufficiently capture the nuances of individual patient profiles, exposing many to either unnecessary treatment or inadequate protection [30].

This review advocates for a dynamic, personalized approach centered around the delta-RCV model, which takes into account the biological variability of CTX and allows for more accurate, patient-

specific decision-making. Combined with the advanced imaging tools, complementary BTMs, and next-generation technologies—such as AI-assisted predictive models—[21][27][28], this framework could significantly improve patient outcomes.

To optimize post-denosumab care, future studies should validate the clinical utility of RCV-guided interventions, assess the long-term impact of emerging therapies like romosozumab or combined therapies [20][26], and explore the integration of AI into real-world clinical algorithms [27][28]. Until such data is available, clinicians should remain vigilant, prioritize individualized risk stratification, and adopt flexible strategies informed by both dynamic biomarkers and comprehensive patient assessment.

As aforementioned, it is essential to adopt a cautious initial prescription of denosumab, and, when appropriate, a valuable option might be extending denosumab treatment beyond the standard 10 years (e.g., for patients at very high fracture risk or with persistent skeletal fragility). Long-term data have shown sustained efficacy and safety for up to 15 years of continuous treatment in appropriately monitored individuals [1][22], suggesting that indefinite therapy may be a viable option in carefully selected cases.

As stated, our delta-RCV framework is a propose; it is a model based on current pathophysiological understanding and clinical experience, and might serve as a foundation for future studies. Prospective validation—particularly through RCTs using incident fracture as the primary endpoint—is urgently needed to confirm its utility and safety. Until such data are available, it is advisable to follow, with clinical ‘‘judgment’’, the most recent expert consensus or statements [5][30]: it is essential to adapt every recommendation to the single patient, because, each patient is unique and does not reflect the average—let alone the median—of a population. Therefore, a rigid, one-size-fits-all approach is rarely clinically optimal in non-acute medical settings.

Figure 1. Synthetic representation of the proposed post-denosumab framework.

Abbreviations: CTX = C-terminal telopeptide of type I collagen; BTMs = Bone turnover markers; Other BTMs = e.g, B-ALP (Bone-specific alkaline phosphatase), P1NP (Procollagen type I N-terminal propeptide); LP/DPD = Lysylpyridinoline/Deoxypyridinoline; tartrate-resistant acid phosphatase 5b (TRAP5b); DXA BMD = bone mineral density evaluated through dual energy X-rays absorptiometry; VFA = vertebral fracture assessment (through DXA scan or Rx rays); TBS = Trabecular bone score; FRAX® = Fracture Risk Assessment Tool; RCV = Reference Change Value (%). Clinical history: patient's characteristics potentially influencing rebound effect (e.g., previous bisphosphonate; incidental fracture; comorbidities; therapies); QUS = quantitative ultrasound; REMS = radiofrequency echographic multi-spectrometry. Treatment could be an amino-bisphosphonate, or in selected case, means restart of denosumab therapy (+/- teriparatide), or switch to others agents (such as romosozumab).

Figure 2. Case n.1 of delta-RCV-based algorithm application post-denosumab.

CTX trajectory in an ideal patient with a baseline value of 0.40 ng/mL and a Reference Change Value (RCV) threshold set at 0.58 ng/mL (45% increase). The trend is immediately linear and clearly rising, with CTX already reaching 0.52 ng/mL by month 2—approaching the clinical alert zone. From month 3 onward (CTX = 0.56 ng/mL), values are near the RCV threshold, signaling a high risk of rebound bone turnover. By month 4, the CTX level (0.60 ng/mL) exceeds the threshold, confirming a significant biological rebound. At this stage, postponing treatment should significantly increase the patient's risk of vertebral fractures. The same approach is applied during follow-up.

Figure 3. Case n. 2 of delta-RCV-based algorithm application post-denosumab.

CTX monitoring in an ideal patient with a baseline of 0.35 ng/mL and a 30% RCV threshold (0.455 ng/mL, 30% due to different laboratory). This chart reflects a less predictable and initially reassuring trajectory. From month 0 to 4, the values fluctuate within a low-risk range, offering no clear cause for alarm. However, beginning around month 5 (CTX = 0.42 ng/mL), the trend shifts upward, entering a biologically concerning zone. By month 7 (CTX = 0.46 ng/mL), the RCV threshold is crossed, marking the first strong indication to consider antiresorptive treatment. Although the CTX briefly declines in month 8, the subsequent months (10 and 11) show sustained elevation above the threshold, confirming a rebound effect. At this stage, postponing treatment should significantly increase the patient's risk of vertebral fractures. The same approach is applied during follow-up.

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Data availability

No datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

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Author Contributions

M.A. conceived, wrote, and reviewed the manuscript, and created the figures. F.M.B., A.V., G.T., and L.A., critically reviewed the work at every stage. All authors reviewed the final version and approved its content in full.

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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